

AMIR TEMUR'S PREPARATIONS FOR THE INDIAN MILITARY CAMPAIGN

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Anotatsiya: This article discusses Amir Temur's military campaign to India and the factors that led to it.

Kays words: China, India, elephant, forest, river, fighting elephant, sword, navkar, sipohi, kanbuls

Amir Temur's military goal and prepared army was intended to be mobilized for the Chinese campaign. However, Prince Muhammad Sultan had to prepare the material base for this campaign - food and fodder. Yazdi also testifies about this: "I was doing azimat in Sahibqiran ul Mahal, go to the infidels of China." When Amir Temur was preparing to go to China, his beggars persuaded him to go to India. At the end of March 1398, he went on a march to India. Mrs. Saraymulk and Ulug'bek also set out with the hosts. After crossing Amudarya, Shahrukh from Herat also joins with his soldiers and stays with his father and son until the middle of August. Amir Timur spends several months fighting with the infidels of old Kafiristan (now Nuristan) in the Hindu Kush mountains in northern Afghanistan before crossing to India. Then in August he will come to Kabul through Andarob. In the middle of this month, he returned Shahrukh to Herat and Ulugbek and Mrs. Saraymulk to Samarkand, and on August 20, he left Kabul and headed for India. He passed away on November 21, 1221 after a battle with Sultan Jalaluddin Khorezmshah Genghis Khan from the Sind River on September 24. At that time, the deserts on the left bank of the river were called Jalali desert. This testified that Amir Temur himself was aware of the history and events of Jalaluddin Khorezmshah, and that memories of the great Khorezmshah were alive in these lands during his time. The battle with

Delhi Sultan Sultan Mahmud Khan Dehlavi will take place on December 17, 1398. Ten thousand cavalry, forty thousand foot and one hundred and twenty elephants will take part in the Indians. Special swords were attached to both tusks of the elephants, and they were trained to swing this sword. In addition, a bronze throne was placed on top of the elephant, and five or six archers were sitting on it.

Between the two elephants, the ball and Hazrat Sahibtsiron's great desire never stopped for a day or night from expanding the sphere of rule and sweeping the territory of the country. Sharafuddin Ali Yazdi was the gunner. The elephants were also clothed. The owner is also well prepared for the battle. He built a fortress of reeds and wood in front of the army. Then the army dug a trench around it and tied the edge of the trench tightly with Indian sheepskin. In addition, Sahibqiran made many iron spikes against elephants. Balls were equipped. The battle did not last long. The enemy could not withstand the attack and pressure of the Chigatai and scattered. Sahibqiran performed the midday prayer near the Delhi Gate. In the battle, the sixteen-year-old Prince Khalil Sultan showed great heroism. Sultan Mahmud Khan Dehlavi was completely defeated and fled. Sahibqiran returned from an eleven-month Indian campaign in the spring of 1399. During his campaign in India, Amir Temur made the intention that if he returns to Samarkand safely, he will build a mosque. Therefore, he ordered to build a mosque in Samarkand. On May 10, 1399, the design of the mosque was drawn up, and two hundred master masons brought from Persia, Azerbaijan and India started work on the same day. Five hundred men were sent to the mountain to cut stone. Ninety-five elephants brought from India were used to bring stone from the mountain.

All the architects and craftsmen known in the country were engaged in work. A prince and a bek were appointed as collectors for each work, apparently, the person in this position was the financial provider of this work. Yazdi writes, "I was very caring of the owner. He was not involved in the work of the mosque, but he came every day and took care of the workers." And most of the avqots were standing in the Khanim madrasa or Tuman Agha's house and praying. On Friday, four

hundred and eighty columns of stone were built, each of which was seven cubits (3.5 meters) long. And they made the roof (ceiling) of stone. After the completion of the mosque, Dilkusho went to the garden and gave weddings. He dressed the craftsmen in robes and put them on horses. At this time, they reported that there was a ruckus in Tabriz related to Prince Mironshokh. At that time, Mironshokh was heavily addicted to alcohol and spent more time with good friends, drunkards and gambling. He even scolded the proud Khanzoda once and even beat him. Khanzoda could not bear this and immediately left for Samarkand in anger. Khanzoda came to Sahibkiran when he received bad news about the situation in Tabriz and said: "If Sahibkiran does not follow his advice, he will do it." My lord, His Highness, took possession of it and distributed everything to his beggars. In the center, the main victory flag of the army was attached to the hand. In front of the ranks of the army, thirty war elephants, captured during the Indian campaign, were lined up.

Various goods from different countries - "China, India, Tatarstan and other countries" were brought to the annual fairs held in Samarkand. During the Timurid period, the exchange of products made by Mowarounnahr and Indian artisans was quite lively. From India, thin white fabrics woven with darning, gazmols called Hyderabad, Gujarat, Banoras fabrics depending on the place of manufacture, as well as sugar. and dyes were brought. Such relations with India developed especially during the period of Zahiruddin Muhammad Babur.

It should be noted that Amir Temur had a habit of celebrating every triumphant and joyful event by building a magnificent architectural monument. For this purpose, skilled builders brought from India, famous master craftsmen from Khorezm, Isfahan, Shiraz, Aleppo and many other cities of the East built beautiful structures in the country.

Every architectural monument built in Samarkand during the time of Amir Temur, from the foundation to the top of the dome, from the tiles to the bricks, had a single, complete and perfectly beautiful appearance. Also, large-scale monumental paintings were painted on the walls of many palaces built during this period. In them,

Amir Temur's triumphant campaigns to India, Iran and Dashti Kipchak, reception ceremonies of ambassadors, conversations with scholars and scholars, wedding and party scenes were very skillfully depicted.

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